

DiSSCo Transition Project

Documentation for the enrolment of DiSSCo services into DiSSCo's federated AAI infrastructure services

Work Package 3 - Milestone 17

Sam Leeflang, Sharif Islam (Naturalis)

Kessy Abarenkov (UTartu)

Grant number 101130121

HORIZON-INFRA-2023-DEV-01-02 — Early phase implementation of ESFRI Projects
which entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2018

HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions - Horizon Europe

16 April 2025

Version 1.1

Table of contents

List of abbreviations	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Overview of the AAI setup	6
2.1. Technical implementation	6
2.2. Authentication	7
2.3. Authorisation	8
3. Integrating with DiSSCo AAI	8
3.1. A step-by-step guide for integrating a human-facing service	9
3.2. A step-by-step guide for integrating a machine agent	10
4. Conclusion and Future Work	11
5. References	12

Project DiSSCo Transition**Grant Agreement n°** 101130121**Start of the project** 01 December 2023**Duration** 18 months**Project Coordinator** Stichting Naturalis Biodiversity Center

Documentation for the enrolment of

Milestone title DiSSCo services into DiSSCo's
federated AAI infrastructure services**Milestone n°** MS17**Means of verification** Document**Work Package** WP3**Lead Beneficiary** University of Tartu**Due date of milestone** 31 January 2025**Actual submission date** 16 April 2025**Quality review** Yes**Milestone status**

Version	Status	Date	Responsible	Actions
0.5	Draft 0.5	20/03/2025	Sharif Islam	Created outline and introduction
0.6	Draft 0.6	25/03/2025	Kessy Abarenkov	Draft improvements
0.9	Draft for review	28/03/2025	Sam Leeflang	Finalise first draft, add figures
1.0	Draft 1.0 review	15/03/2025	Claus Weiland, Wouter Addink	Reviewed
1.0	Draft 1.1	16/03/2025	Sam Leeflang	Finalised, with incorporation of feedback from reviewers
1.1	Final	16/03/2025	Sam Leeflang	Submitted

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This document describes how DiSSCo services can integrate with the existing DiSSCo Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI). During the DiSSCo Prepare Project (DPP) and SYNTHESYS+ project, a centralised DiSSCo AAI has been developed. Within the DiSSCo Transition Project (DTP), work has been done to integrate our first DiSSCo services, the Digital Specimen Architecture (DSArch) and platform for curating and annotating digital specimens (DiSSCover). This deliverable describes the implementation of the AAI and the onboarding process of new DiSSCo services. We identified two flows of onboarding. The first is for human-facing services, which require a login through a third-party identity provider. The second flow is for machine-to-machine communication, where machines request access to DiSSCo services.

Keywords

Authentication, Authorisation, Identify and Access Management, Keycloak, Application Programming Interfaces, DiSSCo Services, ORCID

List of abbreviations

AAI - Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure

AARC - Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration

API - Application Programming Interface

CA - Consortium Agreement

D - Deliverable

DiSSCo - Distributed System of Scientific Collections

DPP - DiSSCo Prepare Project

DSArch - Digital Specimen Architecture

DTP - DiSSCo Transition Project

ELIXIR - European life sciences infrastructure

GA - Grant Agreement

GBIF - Global Biodiversity Information Facility

IAM - Identity and Access Management

IDP - Identity Provider

JWT - JSON Web Tokens

MS - Milestone

MAS - Machine Annotation Service

OIDC - OpenID Connect

OAuth2 - Open Authorisation version 2.0

PID - Persistent Identifier

RBAC - Role Based Access Control

RFC - Request For Comments

RI - Research Infrastructure

SSO - Single Sign-On

WP - Work Package

1. Introduction

As DiSSCo advances towards full operational readiness, a robust and well-documented authentication and authorisation infrastructure is essential to ensure secure and seamless access across services. Building upon the work carried out in SYNTHESYS+ and DiSSCo Prepare Project (DPP), we have implemented an Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) based on Keycloak. This system is operational and integrated with a platform for curating and annotating digital specimens ([DiSSCover](#)) and the Digital Specimen Architecture (DSArch) as part of DiSSCo Transition Project (DTP) Deliverable 3.1 (Minimum Viable Product of Core Infrastructure).

The purpose of this document is to provide an overview of the current setup and to outline guidelines for integrating additional services into DiSSCo's AAI. Specifically, it will detail the necessary steps for service providers to authenticate their services with DiSSCo's AAI. While further refinements and policy alignments are ongoing, this document serves as a practical guide for current and future DiSSCo services to establish secure authentication and authorisation mechanisms.

2. Overview of the AAI setup

Authentication and authorisation plays a key role for all services in the DiSSCo infrastructure. Authentication refers to the process of signing in as a registered user, whereas authorisation refers to the rights and permissions to perform certain actions a user has. From the user's perspective, it is desired that a user can log in to all DiSSCo services with the same credentials through single sign-on (SSO). User's authorisation will be managed by the Identity and Access Management (IAM), where Role Based Access Control (RBAC) will be used to determine a user's permission within the system.

During the SYNTHESYS+ project, Task 6.1 created a design document for AAI infrastructure (Addink et al. 2020). This design was implemented for ELViS (European Loans and Visits System), one of DiSSCo's services (Leeflang et al. 2023b). In addition, within the DiSSCo Prepare Project (DPP), a plan was developed to integrate the DSArch and DiSSCover with the AAI (Leeflang et al. 2022).

Building on the research and experience of SYNTHESYS+ and DPP projects, in DTP the Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure was further developed and integrated in both the DSArch and DiSSCover. Further in the document, we will describe the guidelines for integration with other DiSSCo services, both human and machine-facing.

2.1. Technical implementation

For the technical implementation of DiSSCo's AAI, research within SYNTHESYS+ had shown that an AARC blueprint architecture-compatible solution using Keycloak would be the preferred option (Addink et al. 2020). Keycloak is an open-source Identity Access Management (IAM) tool.¹ Instead of each application implementing user authentication

¹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

and authorisation themselves, Keycloak centralises this task. It provides a single point where users and machines can log in, and it securely stores and processes credentials. Due to its centralised nature, it can provide SSO capabilities, ensuring a user only needs to log in once to get access to the whole suite of DiSSCo services. Users, roles and groups are centrally managed by an administrator. Keycloak also provides the required functionality to integrate with third-party identity providers such as ORCID, EduGain and Google.

For the communication of confidential information, Keycloak uses [OAuth2](#) protocol. This industry-standard protocol creates a standardised and simple way to ensure safe access to restricted resources. On top of OAuth2, we will use OpenID Connect ([OIDC](#)) for user authentication.

Within DiSSCo, we use the data policy “As open as possible, as closed as necessary” (Hardisty 2019). This means that we will try to keep all data accessible to everyone, but we might have some data or actions for which a user needs to be authenticated and/or authorised. Examples are the addition of new source systems, the scheduling of a Machine Annotation Service ([MAS](#)) or the approval of an annotation. As all actions within DiSSCo are made through specific endpoints, each endpoint that contains a restricted action is secured behind the AAI.

2.2. Authentication

For the authentication within DiSSCo, we will not develop our own authentication capabilities. Authentication will solely be done through third-party Identity Providers (IDPs). This means that a user won't need to create a new account and DiSSCo won't require storing additional secure information such as passwords.

Within DiSSCo, it is important that we are able to attribute a user's action back to the user through a unique global persistent identifier (PID). Instead of developing our own unique global user identifiers, we will rely on an ORCID for this (Haak et al. 2012). ORCID is a global infrastructure providing free, unique, persistent identifiers for individuals to use as they engage in research, scholarship, and innovation activities. Not only does this connect each user to a unique PID, it also provides us with the possibility to feed the user provenance to other systems.

Besides an integration with ORCID, we will also provide integrations for Google and the institutions' identity providers, through EduGAIN. Both these approaches have advantages, however, we will still require a user to connect their ORCID before any new information can be provided to the DiSSCo infrastructure. More IDPs may be added in the future in a federated way, depending on user needs, for example, RIs like GBIF and ELIXIR could be candidates.

2.3. Authorisation

Authorisation is done through a Role Based Authentication Control (RBAC). Roles can be defined and connected to a user in the AAI. When a user logs in, the application will

retrieve the roles from the AAI. The application can then check if the required role matches the roles associated with the user. It will then either allow the user the action or indicate that the user does not have sufficient permissions. This provides a fine-grained mechanism to control a user's access, as well as provides the possibility to slowly release new features. Each new DiSSCo capability can be assigned a role and slowly opened up to the public. Besides RBAC, we will also use groups to control a user's authorisation. Each user can be in one or more groups, and one or more roles can be attached to this group. An example could be a DiSSCo administrator group in which all DiSSCo administrators will be added. This group will get higher authorisation, so it will contain most, if not all, available roles. As a best practice, DiSSCo will ask service providers to only assign roles to groups instead of individual users to keep better track of authorisation.

3. Integrating with DiSSCo AAI

Within DiSSCo's AAI, we identify two types of DiSSCo services: human-facing services and machine agents (Figure 1). Human-facing services are applications where users must log in to interact with information. These applications require a login screen where users authenticate themselves before accessing data through a graphical user interface. DiSSCover serves as our primary example of this flow, being DiSSCo's first front-end application fully integrated into DiSSCo's AAI. Other human-facing DiSSCo services, such as ELViS, will soon follow.

This flow differs from machine authentication with the DiSSCo infrastructure. Machines require alternative authentication methods before they can interact with DiSSCo's data. While most examples remain hidden from users, several services within the DSArch communicate with each other through this flow. In this chapter, we will explain both authentication flows.

Figure 1. Diagram showing the two different integration flows. In red, the flow for a human-facing service such as DiSSCover. In purple, the flow for a machine service.

3.1. A step-by-step guide for integrating a human-facing service

We will start with the flow for a human-facing service (Figure 2). As mentioned, for authorisation, we will make use of the OAuth2 protocol. This industry-standard protocol creates a standardised and simple way to ensure safe access to restricted resources. On top of OAuth2, we will use OpenID Connect (OIDC) for user authentication. OIDC provides information about the user that has logged in through claims, for example her/his email address. OIDC uses encoded JSON Web Tokens (JWT) which contain information about the users.

When a new human-facing service wants to connect to the DiSSCo AAI, it will need to redirect users for their login to DiSSCo's Keycloak. This is most often done through the implementation of an existing library, such as the [Keycloak JavaScript adapter](#). This adapter will help developers in creating a secure connection with Keycloak. An example of the Keycloak JavaScript adapter can be found in the [DiSSCover repository](#).

Once the user is redirected to Keycloak, they will need to select their preferred third-party identity provider (ORCID, Google or their institutional identity provider), which will let Keycloak redirect them to the specific identity provider. There, the user can provide their credentials and authenticate themselves. The identity provider will then redirect the user back to Keycloak which will attach existing information to the JWT, such as a user's ORCID. This JWT will be returned to the front-end, allowing it to be used for any protected actions the user is about to make, where it will be added as a bearer token². Within OAuth2 this flow is called an "Authorisation Code Flow" (Hardt 2012, section 4.1).

² A token is an opaque string to authorise access to a resource. The term "bearer" signifies that everyone in possession of the token is entitled to access the resource.

Figure 2. Sequence diagram describing the subsequent steps a human-facing service will follow to authenticate and authorise a user. In the alt blocks are the exception flows.

3.2. A step-by-step guide for integrating a machine agent

For machines, there is a slightly different flow (Figure 3). A machine does not have an account with an identity provider. Therefore, DiSSCo cannot use third-party identity providers to facilitate the authentication process. For machine-to-machine interaction, we will use the “Client Credentials Flow” (Hardt 2012, section 4.4). This flow will be both used for external machines requesting DiSSCo data and internal services (Leeflang et al. 2023a). Within Keycloak, we will create a special client called a service account for the machine agent. This will let Keycloak create a client identifier and a generated client secret for the machine agent. With this client identifier and client secret, a machine agent can authenticate itself with Keycloak and retrieve a bearer token. These tokens must then be included in any restricted API calls the machine will make as an HTTP header. Service

accounts can be assigned specific roles, which means the RBAC system in place for users can also be used for machines.

Figure 3. Sequence diagram describing the subsequent steps a machine agent will follow to authenticate and authorise a user. In the alt blocks are the exception flows.

4. Conclusion and Future Work

During the DiSSCo Transition Project, we have integrated several DiSSCo services with DiSSCo's AAI. We identified two flows of integrating with the DiSSCo's AAI. Both flows of enrolment into DiSSCo's federated AAI have been implemented and tested. In this document, we described how additional DiSSCo services will be able to integrate and leverage DiSSCo's AAI.

While the current AAI infrastructure provides a robust authentication and authorisation framework, several challenges remain. Integration with IdPs such as ORCID, EduGain, and institutional logins requires alignment with EOSC and Authentication and Authorisation for Research and Collaboration ([AARC](#)) recommendations, as support for federated authentication varies across institutions. Additionally, the authorisation model, while centrally managed through Keycloak, still requires standardised role definitions to ensure consistent access control across DiSSCo services. Additionally, while ORCID is valuable for linking researcher identities and profile information, it may not apply to non-researcher users. Services targeting broader audiences will need to ensure that authentication and

authorisation mechanisms can accommodate users without ORCIDs. Each service might need to implement its own policies, which may lead to additional configuration overhead. Developers working on the integration will provide feedback and additional use cases through which we can enhance the onboarding process and further refine our AAI.

Furthermore, evolving European regulations on digital identity and security may require future modifications to maintain compliance with GDPR and other policies. Some of these issues, particularly those related to access and governance, will be further addressed in the DiSSCo Data Policy and Access and Employment Policies, which are being developed as part of separate DTP milestones.

5. References

Haak, L. L., Fenner, M., Paglione, L., Pentz, E., & Ratner, H. (2012). ORCID: a system to uniquely identify researchers. In *Learned Publishing* (Vol. 25, Issue 4, pp. 259–264). Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1087/20120404>

Hardisty, Alex. (2019). Provisional Data Management Plan for DiSSCo infrastructure. Deliverable D6.6. ICEDIG. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3532937>

Hardt, D. (Ed.). (2012). The OAuth 2.0 Authorization Framework. RFC Editor. <https://doi.org/10.17487/rfc6749>

Leeflang, S, Weiland, C, Grieb, J, Dillen, M, Islam, S, Fichtmueller, D, Addink, W, & Haston, E (2022). DiSSCo Prepare D6.2 Implementation and construction plan of the DiSSCo core architecture (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6832200>

Leeflang, S., Weiland, C., Islam, S., Dillen, M., & Theocharides, S. (2023a). DiSSCo Prepare Deliverable D6.3 - A generalised set of API specifications for interaction with the DiSSCo core architecture. DiSSCo Prepare. <https://doi.org/10.34960/HTZV-NW73>

Leeflang, S., Liampotis, N., Georgilakis, C. & Islam, S. (2023b). D6.2 Piloting Access Through an AAI infrastructure. SYNTHESYS PLUS.

Wouter A., Islam S., Koumantaros K. , Laskaris N. (2020). MS48 AAI Infrastructure Design. SYNTHESYS PLUS <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/HKEBA>